

An Analytical Study of Aarogya Setu App and Visual Media Communication with its Effective Communication among the Indians

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Abstract: As been like most other countries in the world, India also battling against the Covid-19 pandemic for the past few months. To control over the spread of Corona Virus, Indian Prime Minister Narendra Modi called for a complete nationwide lockdown from March 25th 2020 and to till date with some lockdown liberation. While dealing with the nation to inform billions of Indians about this extension, the government of India also asked every citizen to download and use a mobile-based application, named Arogya Setu app.

Social distancing and wearing mask in the common place has become the new custom for most Indians today, amidst this pandemic. At such a time, people need to stay updated regarding containment zones, virus hotspots and more related useful Covid 19 information. This Arogya Setu app is a government initiative to ensure the utmost safety and awareness for its citizens from this deadly virus. In essence, this digital application connects Indian health services to its people at this impulsive time.

Scientific and technological research is directly linked to social welfare, the economy and global sustainability. New media, accessed through mobile phones are providing opportunities for a wide range of citizens to engage with new developments in science communication. These media provide opportunities for citizens to learn about more recent and rational issues in the social context.

The study is to be done to analyse the digital application (Aarogya Setu App) and to find its effective communication among the people of India. And also analyse how other visual communication creates an awareness among every citizens in India during pandemic. In such a world, increasing the public's understanding and appreciation of science and technology is of vital importance. Increasingly, this tension has interfered with scientific progress, the quality of science education and broader ability of the scientific enterprise to fully serve the needs of society.

1. INTRODUCTION

The main purpose the Aarogya setu App is to create awareness about the COVID 19 among the nationals and to connect with essential health related

information and communication among the people. Almost of the population were connected with digital communication through smart phones, hence this app initiated to spread the awareness. Thus it becomes the best practices and health advisories. Also it was advantageous in tracking and finding the infected persons in the particular area.

Today, recent modern media technologies are complementing each other in communicating the society. Now a day's digital media are the most important vehicles of social change. While a lot of adaptation may be needed to convey social as well as health messages to large number of people. When Aarogya Setu was launched it crossed five million downloads within few days of its launch, building it was one of the most popular government apps in India.

Digital media in India are an effective and important part of the communication system in recent times. These are unique in nature, as they resemble the day-to-day life pattern of the large masses. These media are a source of education and information to create awareness and the knowledge such app was developed to update the COVID 19 information during the pandemic. The digital media have been able to aid in national development for a longer time. Most of the app users were literally connected each other with the necessary communication, and also tends to get more knowledge about the vaccination. Thus this situation entails to study the importance and impact of Aarogya setu app among the people by adopting focus group discussion among the users to find the effective results.

1.1 Objective

1. To understand the effective communication given through the Aarogya setu app.
2. To find the impact created by the Aarogya setu app among its users.

2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The focus group discussion research method was adopted to find the effective communication and the impact of the Aarogya setu app among the people in qualitative approach in a descriptive manner. The samples were the app users, identified technically over the Chennai region. Around 15 users were involved in the focus group discussion. Both male and female respondents of age group between 25 to 40 years with different professionals were included for the group discussion, researcher was the moderator. The semi structured questions were asked to find the objective and its results. The simple random purposive sampling technique was adopted to find the exact samples for the discussion.

3. ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS

The focus group discussion was conducted among the selected samples and found the following effective results as responded by the respondents.

- During the pandemic social distancing was the important norm were instructed to all the citizens to amidst during COVID 19 strictly. The Aarogya setu app becomes one of the important tools to get updated with covid information.
- This app is recommended by the government as a health communication initiative to ensure every citizens are safe from deadly corona virus. The essence of its application is to connect our nation's health services to the people during pandemic.
- By tracing the contact, covid affected area is notified and intimated highrisk or hotspot area to users, also informed the users to procure with the essential measures to avoid the epidemic disease.
- App kept informed the users to follow standard precautionary against covid infections to all the members in the family.
- App facilitates the users to understand the current situations associated with the covid and act as a platform to self-diagnosis and allows them to take decision to consult doctor.
- App has supported in eleven languages, including regional languages across India was benefited by many citizens.
- The foremost purpose of the app is to create awareness on the safety guidelines to avoid infection and paves way to conduct self assessment to determine about the symptomatic of coronavirus.
- Guidelines and health related informations are mostly updated during the pandemic to minimise the health risk. Additionally this app was updated

with e-pass facility for the people to mobilise from one place to other place.

4. CONCLUSION

During the nationwide lock down period and the pandemic situation people maintained social distancing to avoid the spread of the deadly virus. But every citizen felt safe due to awareness created by the media and digital communication in the society. The digital applications and communication has reduced the hassle of knowledge and awareness related to the covid 19. People are digitally connected to each other to fight against corona virus and thus situation made with greater ease.

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